

EU-HYBNET Meta-Analysis Survey Instrument for Evaluating the Effects of Disinformation and the Effectiveness of counter-responses

[Rubén Arcos](#), [Manuel Gertrudix](#) & [Cristina Arribas](#) (Ciberimaginario Research Group - [University Rey Juan Carlos](#), Spain)

[Empowering a Pan-European Network to Counter Hybrid Threats](#)

Project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No883054

Please, analyze relevant articles or reports from institutions, think-tanks or fact-checkers focused, either on disinformation effects or on the effects of counter-disinformation initiatives (fact-checking, debunking)

There are 40 questions in this survey

[]What is the title of the article/report? *

Please write your answer here:

[]Author (s) *

Please write your answer here:

Write the authors as follows: Surname, first name.

When there is more than one author, separate each one with a semicolon ;

[]Indicate, where applicable, the URL

Please write your answer here:

[]

What is the object of the inquiry, the subject of study, or research topic/issue under consideration?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Disinformation effects and/or impact
- Misinformation effects and/or impact
- Disinformation and misinformation effects and/or impact
- Disinformation as part of hybrid threats
- Fact-checking effectiveness
- Debunking effectiveness
- Measuring exposure to dis- and misinformation

Note: Disinformation effects include: cognitive, affective and behavioral effects

[]

What is the academic discipline or field of study from which the research is approached?

*

Check all that apply

Only numbers may be entered in 'Other:' accompanying text field.

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Communication studies
- Journalism
- Political science ad international relations
- Security and intelligence studies
- Terrorism studies
- Psychology
- Health sciences
- Other:

Note: Select the main discipline from which the study is approached.

[]

What kind of study?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Analytic
- Comparative research
- Descriptive
- Explanatory
- Participatory research
- NC/NP

Indicate the type of research it is:

- Descriptive. What are the characteristics of a phenomenon, what it is like, how it varies over time, how it appears ...
- Comparative. How it manifests itself in two or more areas, groups, etc.
- Analytics. What are the elements that make up the phenomenon.
- Explanatory. What are the causes that originated it, why does it occur, what consequences does it have ...
- Participatory. How to intervene to modify the phenomenon, its results, etc.

[]

What are the aims of the article/report?

Please write your answer here:

[]

**Does the study explicitly declare the hypotheses?
What are these if indicated?**

Please write your answer here:

[]

What is the universe or population under study?

*

Please write your answer here:

Note: In the event that it is not indicated explicitly and cannot be deduced from the information, you must write:

"The universe of study is not explicitly indicated"

[]

What is the sampling technique used?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- NA - Not applicable
- Sample not indicated
- Structural. Non-probabilistic sampling.
- Intentional
- Probabilistic
- Significant of population

If the question does not apply, select NA - Not applicable.

Otherwise, select one of the following:

- **Structural.** Non-probabilistic sampling. The sample is composed looking for saturation and not probability. It is common in conversational techniques in which it is sought to know the discourse of a social group (interviews, discussion groups, etc.)
- **Intentional or of convenience.** Non-probabilistic sampling. The sample consists of "representative" cases of typical groups or those that are easily accessible.
- **Probabilistics.** Sampling in which all individuals have the same probability of be chosen to be part of a sample and, consequently, is representative of the population.
- **Significant population.** Probability sampling. The sample represents the total population representing its structure. They contain a large random sample and a high response rate.

[]What is the sample size?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Structural. Non-probabilistic sampling.' or 'Intentional' or 'Significant of population' or 'Probabilistic' at question '10

[G1Q00017]' (What is the sampling technique used?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Between 1 and 50
- Between 51 and 100
- Between 101 and 200
- Between 201 and 500
- More than 501

[]

What is the main information/data gathering technique?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Collection of documents or audiovisual/digital media materials (i.e. tweets, posts, YouTube videos, Whatsapp messages)
- Interviews
- Surveys
- Experiments
- Direct observation
- Other:

[]

What kind of data has been obtained and how was obtained?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Qualitative
- Quantitative
- Observation
- Experimental
- Simulations
- Other:

[]

What theories and/or frameworks are referenced?

Please write your answer here:

- Indicate if specific theories are pointed out
- If there is more than one, separate with commas
- If none is specified, indicate NA (Not applicable)

[]

What are the analysis techniques used?

*

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

Qualitative

Quantitative

Social network analysis

Sentiment analysis

Other

S4. Digital Mis- and Disinformation and counter measures effects

[]

What are the main findings and conclusions reported. Please summarize in the box below.

*

Please write your answer here:

[]

Any reference to mis- or disinformation as part of hybrid threats/influence operations/or information warfare?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

[]

Does the article have a neutral approach to dis- misinformation?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No, the analysis takes into account the political dimension including causes and intentions
 Other:

[]

Any particular mention to...?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- State actors (i.e. Russia, China, Iran, North Korea...)
 Non-state actors linked or aligned with aligned with foreign governments
 Other:

[]

Is it a regional or country case study?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

[]

Please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '20 [S4005]' (Is it a regional or country case study?)

Please write your answer here:

[]

Does the article mentions/analyzes any of the following aims of disinformation?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Confusing the target
- Deceive the target
- Increasing uncertainty of the receiver about facts
- Information overload of the receiver
- Persuasion towards a partisan political option
- Sowing mistrust against government authorities or institutions
- Sowing mistrust against particular communities (example: immigrants)
- Reflexive control or perception management
- Other:

[]

Does the article mentions/analyzes any of the following strategies?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Conspiracy theories
- Deepfakes (AI-generated photos, videos, sounds, texts)
- Leak of apparently official documents

- Manipulation of images and other audiovisual materials (Photoshopped-like edited photos and videos)
- Micro-targeting
- Revisionism of history
- Other:

[]

Do the documents analyzed in the sample include?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Apparently analytic pieces
- Fake news stories (hard news)
- Opinion pieces either with unintentional or intentional misleading information
- Opinionated retweets/posts distorting the meaning of the original news story
- Public commentary of news stories published by digital news media (i.e. comments by readers)
- Other:

[]

What strategies do the sample messages adopt?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Emotional persuasion
- Rational persuasion
- Both

[]

Are there references to the authenticity of the sources? If so what kind of source strategy do the disinformation messages employ?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- No references
- Attributed but already known sources to be unreliable or serving the interest of particular actors
- Bots

- Declared and official sources
- Fake personas
- Unattributed sources
- Other:

[]

What mis-and disinformation effects are reported?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Cognitive (message exposure, message understanding, message retention)
- Affective (interest and generating negative or positive attitudes towards institutions, organizations, people)
- Behavior (do or stop doing something)
- Other:

[]

Is there any particular metric employed or an evaluation technique used to evaluate the impact of mis- and disinformation?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

[]Please specify which one

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '28 [S4b0022]' (Is there any particular metric employed or an evaluation technique used to evaluate the impact of mis- and disinformation?)

Please write your answer here:

[]

Is the article focused on fact-checking or debunking effectiveness?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

[]

Is the article focused on the effectiveness of fact-checking in target audiences taken at face value or

does the study conduct an evaluation of its impact (beliefs, attitudes, behavior) in target audiences?

If affirmative, please indicate what of the following two options fit better

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Not applicable
- The effectiveness of fact-checking and/or debunking is taken at face value
- The study conducts an evaluation on the impact (beliefs, attitudes, behavior) of fact-checking/debunking in target audiences

[]What type of evaluation?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'The study conducts an evaluation on the impact (beliefs, attitudes, behavior) of fact-checking/debunking in target audiences' at question '31 [S4013]' (Is the article focused on the effectiveness of fact-checking in target audiences taken at face value or does the study conduct an evaluation of its impact (beliefs, attitudes, behavior) in target audiences? If affirmative, please indicate what of the following two options fit better)

Please write your answer here:

[]

Is there any particular metric employed or an evaluation technique used to evaluate the impact of fact-checking or debunking?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

[]Please specify which one.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '33 [S4011]' (Is there any particular metric employed or an evaluation technique used to evaluate the impact of fact-checking or debunking?)

Please write your answer here:

[]

What message strategies and tools are employed when debunking?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Debunking effectiveness' at question '4 [G1Q00003]' (What is the object of the inquiry, the subject of study, or research topic/issue under consideration?)

Please write your answer here:

[]

Are there any references to inoculation against dis- and misinformation?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

[] Please specify which one.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '36 [S4016]' (Are there any references to inoculation against dis- and misinformation?)

Please write your answer here:

[]

What message strategies and/or tools are reported to be used when debunking (example: humour, satire)?

*

Please write your answer here:

[]

Is there any reference to the backfire effect?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

[]

What channels are reported to be used when debunking?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Debunking effectiveness' at question '4 [G1Q00003]' (What is the object of the inquiry, the subject of study, or research topic/issue under consideration?)

Please write your answer here:

i.e: posts on websites, Tweets, WhatsApp messages